

Correlation coefficients^a between tolerance index (TI) and other attributes of rice at early seedling stage. IRRI, 1986.

Character	Seedling height on			Discoloration score on			Survival (%) on		TI based on survival on	
	Day 8	Day 15	Day 22	Day 8	Day 15	Day 22	Day 15	Day 22	Day 15	Day 22
Emergence coefficient	0.661**	0.310**	0.194	-0.315**	-0.141	-0.093	0.115	-0.031	0.141	0.084
Seedling height, day 8		0.555**	0.541**	-0.471**	-0.375**	-0.292**	0.257**	0.023	0.322**	0.225**
Seedling height, day 15			0.869**	-0.877**	-0.857**	-0.807**	0.808**	0.520**	0.836**	0.749**
Seedling height, day 22				-0.819**	-0.789**	-0.789**	0.732**	0.567**	0.770**	0.743**
Discoloration score, day 8					0.892**	0.869**	-0.834**	-0.564**	-0.869**	-0.793**
Discoloration score, day 15						0.938**	-0.889**	-0.634**	-0.931**	-0.814**
Discoloration score, day 22							-0.932**	-0.716**	-0.956**	-0.883**
Survival (%) day 15								0.707**	0.981**	0.899**
Survival (%) day 22									0.695**	0.798**
TI based on survival, day 15										0.907**

^a * = significant at P < 0.05, ** = significant at P < 0.01 levels.

tolerance and to determine interrelationships, if any, between traits used as evaluation criteria.

Twelve presprouted seeds, 1 row per culture, were sown in soil-filled porcelain trays with adequate nutrient and water, and then kept in artificially lighted Koiotron KG cabinets at 15 ± 0.5 °C for 3 wk. Each tray contained 10 test cultures and the resistant check Fujisaka 5 distributed at random. There were two replications.

Emergence data were recorded every 4 h for 12 d. The seedlings were scored

as emerged when the shoot tip was visible on the soil surface. An emergence coefficient was worked out based on speed and vigor of emergence. The cultures were scored for discoloration (1 = plants have natural color, 9 = almost dead or dead plants) at 8, 15, and 22 d. Seedling height of the seedlings in a culture was also measured. Survival percentage of the emerged seedlings was recorded at 15 and 22 d on a scale of 0-1. The sum of survival scores for each culture per replication was converted to a percentage of the

average score of Fujisaka 5.

TI, emergence coefficient, seedling height, and discoloration scores were the criteria used for evaluating genotypes for cold tolerance at the early seedling stage.

Intercharacter associations between TI and other traits are shown in the table. TI or cold tolerance at early seedling stage is positively correlated with seedling height at 15 and 22 d, negatively correlated with leaf discoloration score at 8, 15, and 22 d, and positively correlated with percent survival at 15 and 22 d. *ℳ*

Evaluation of rice genotypes for cold tolerance at vegetative stage

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Ninety F₁ hybrids and their 21 parents were transplanted in 2.25-m single-row plots, with 3 replications, in the cold tolerance screening nursery at the CES, RDA, Chuncheon. Plants were subjected to cold water stress at 17 and 20 °C in separate blocks from 20 d after transplanting until maturity at a constant water depth of 5 cm. Cold tolerance at the vegetative stage was measured by leaf discoloration, scored twice at 17 °C and once at 20 °C. The average of the three observations were used for statistical analyses.

None of the six IRRI lines used as pollinators had a leaf discoloration score of 3 or lower (Table 1). Among the

Table 1. Mean and general combining ability (GCA) effects of parents for leaf discoloration score in Chuncheon, Korea, 1986.

Parent	Mean	GCA effects
Males (IRRI lines)		
IR29506-60-3-3-2	5.4	-0.455**
IR8455-K2	5.4	-0.213**
IR9202-10-2-1-5-1	5.8	0.047
IR8866-30-14	5.9	0.496**
IR7167-33-2-3	6.3	-0.147*
IR15889-32-1	6.4	-0.022
		SE (gi) ± 0.069
Females (indica)		
Leng Kwang	3.4	0.716**
Shoa-Nan-Tsan	4.2	1.610**
Suweon 281	4.5	0.566**
Silewah	5.2	0.627**
Samgangbyeon	5.5	0.655**
K39-96-3-1-1-1-2	5.6	1.960**
China 988	6.3	1.938**
Females (japonica)		
Stejaree	1.3	-1.023**
SR3044-78-3	1.3	-0.845**
SR5204-914-1	1.5	-1.051**
Shimokita	1.7	-1.379**
K84	1.7	-1.084**
Barkat	1.8	-0.995**
K332	2.0	-0.990**
Suweon 235	2.0	-0.706**
	LSD 5% = 0.74	SE (gi) ± 0.109
	LSD 1% = 0.98	

Table 2. Correlation coefficients of cold tolerance scores in the field in Korea with traits related to cold tolerance at early seedling and seedling stages in controlled environment at IRRI, 1986.

Characters correlated ^a	Cold tolerance score in field
	<i>r</i> coefficient
<i>Early seedling stage</i>	
Emergence coefficient	-0.191**
Seedling height, day 8	-0.370**
Seedling height, day 15	-0.640**
Seedling height, day 22	-0.570**
Cold tolerance score, day 8	0.692**
Cold tolerance score, day 15	0.753**
Cold tolerance score, day 22	0.746**
TI based on 15 d survival	-0.758**
TI based on 22 d survival	-0.684**
<i>Seedling stage</i>	
Cold tolerance score after first cold water treatment	0.680**
Cold tolerance score after second cold water treatment	0.823**
TI based on revival 5 d after first treatment	-0.699**
TI based on revival 10 d after first treatment	-0.722**
TI based on final survival after second treatment	-0.771**

^a TI = tolerance index (integrates both cold tolerance score and percent revival or survival, relative to the resistant check).

indica females, Leng Kwang had the best score of 3.4. All japonica parents, however, had mean cold tolerance scores below 3. Notable cultures were Stejaree 45, SR3044-78-3, SR5204-91-4-1, Shimokita, K84, and Barkat.

Parental performance per se was a good index of their general combining ability (GCA) for leaf discoloration in the field ($r = 0.712^{**}$). The japonica parents exhibited highly significant GCA effects for low leaf discoloration (high cold tolerance). IR29506 and IR8455-K2 were the only male parents with highly significant GCA effects for low score. The development of cold-tolerant, homozygous lines should be possible through simple selection pressures, and japonicas would be good donors for seedling stage cold tolerance. Of 48 crosses showing specific combining ability (SCA) effects in the desired direction (low score), only 7 were significant. With the exception of China 988/IR8455-K2, SR3044-78-3/IR7167, and Shoa-Nan-Tsan/IR29506, where one of the parents was a good general combiner for cold tolerance, all other good and significant

SCA combinations involved at least one parent with significantly poor GCA. High SCA values would not necessarily mean a high performance by the hybrid. Selection of cold-tolerant hybrids on the basis of performance per se appears more realistic.

At IRRI, cultures at the early seedling stage were screened in the phytotron at a constant temperature of 15 °C for 3 wk, and at the seedling stage by the cold-water tank method at a constant temperature of 12 °C for 10 d. All traits scored in the field in Korea and in the controlled environment at IRRI were highly significantly correlated. Except

Chlorophyll meter (SPAD-501) to quantify relative cold tolerance in rice

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One effect of low temperature on rice is leaf discoloration due to chlorophyll degradation. Quantifying relative cold tolerance by measuring extracted chlorophyll is tedious and time consuming. This study was conducted to evaluate the use of a new chlorophyll meter (Minolta SPAD-501) to quantitatively assess relative cold tolerance in rice. The meter is simple to use and operates on alternating current or batteries. By inserting a leaf into a slit at the head of the instrument and pressing a button, one gets an instant reading.

IR8 and Fujisaka 5 seedlings were grown in culture solution for 34 d in the greenhouse and then held in the cold water tank (12°C) for 7 d. Initially, three readings were taken 12 cm from the tip of the first fully developed leaf or second to the youngest leaf (leaf no. 6). Subsequent readings at the same position were taken on the 4th and 7th

SPAD-501 reading of chlorophyll content of IR8 and Fujisaka 5 at 12°C. IRRI, 1986.

Variety	Spad-501 reading		
	Initial	4th day	7th day
IR8	30.0	27.1	22.5
Fujisaka 5	30.5	29.1	28.2

for the association with emergence coefficient and seedling height on day 8, all other associations were of high magnitude (Table 2). Evidently the test cultures behaved consistently in the controlled environment or in the field. Results also indicate that performance in the controlled environment was a good indicator of field performance. Both methods appear equally effective in ranking cultures for cold temperature tolerance at the vegetative stage. For a quick determination of cold temperature tolerance at the seedling stage, however, the cold-water tank method appears highly satisfactory. *J*

Correlation between chlorophyll content determined by DMSO method and chlorophyll reading from SPAD-501. IRRI, 1986.

days. After 4 d of cold water treatment, the SPAD-501 reading of cold-susceptible IR8 decreased from 30 to 27.1, while in cold-tolerant Fujisaka 5, the readings decreased only slightly — from 30.5 to 29.1 although no color change could be detected by the unaided eye at that time (see table). The trend continued in the readings on the 7th day.

Additional data were collected at 2 temperatures (12 and 30° C) during measurement. The results indicate that temperature during measurement did not affect chlorophyll reading, suggesting that SPAD-501 can be used under high or low temperatures.

Leaf samples were taken from plants having different degrees of yellowing. The chlorophyll content was extracted by dimethyl-sulfoxide (DMSO) method. There was a very high correlation ($r =$